

A New Efficient, Highly Dispersed, Pd Nanoparticulate Silica Supported Catalyst Synthesized from an Organometallic Precursor. Study of the Homogeneous vs. Heterogeneous Activity in the Suzuki-Miyaura Reaction.

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Abstract

A new Pd(0) catalyst supported on silica UVM-7 has been synthesized from the organometallic $[\text{Pd}_2\{\mu\text{-(C}_6\text{H}_4\text{)PPh}_2\}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4](\text{BF}_4)_2$ precursor, characterized by the high dispersion, activity, and small size of the palladium nanoclusters fixed on the silica surface. The catalyst was tested for the Suzuki-Miyaura (SM) reaction of different 4-substitutedphenyl halides with phenylboronic acid. The kinetic study concurs with most of the catalytic action was carried out by Pd species originated by the partial solubilization of Pd immobilized on mesoporous silica. The Schmidt's analysis of differential selectivity (SADS) in several competitive SM reactions, together the STEM-HAADF and HRTEM images of the catalyst surface taken along several reuse cycles support the conclusions of the kinetic study. Furthermore, this hypothesis was critically investigated using different classic approaches to distinguish between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis as the three phases test, poisoning, and hot filtrate experiments.

Keywords: Suzuki-Miyaura, Palladium nanoparticles, UVM-7 silica, Heterogeneous Homogeneous Catalysis, Kinetic study, STEM-HAADF, HRTEM, XRD.

1. Introduction

The separation between the homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis lately seems less defined.^{1,2} Some catalysts in solution, traditionally considered as homogeneous, exhibit a behavior characteristic of a heterogeneous one (precursors of metal NPs), while some catalysts considered heterogeneous behave as homogeneous (leaching of the active species from solid to solution). At the frontier, the catalysis by metal NPs emerges as a bridge between both disciplines, gathering the advantages of a high reactivity and the use of lower amounts of the metal (homeopathic doses).³⁻⁵ This domain is sometimes called "semiheterogeneous", being the field of the nanocatalysis.⁶⁻¹⁰ Furthermore, the immobiliza-

tion of metal NPs on inorganic, organic, or hybrid supports adds the classic advantages of the heterogeneous catalysis to the bottom-up approach of NP synthesis.⁸

Carbon-carbon coupling reactions represent a very important class of organic transformations and palladium is the most widely used metal in these reactions. The heterogenization of palladium compounds grew quickly in the 1970s. Palladium as NPs or complexes were immobilized in many supports.¹¹⁻¹⁶ These latter, under the catalytic coupling conditions, suffer generally a degradation giving in situ NPs. Although at the beginning many catalytic studies paid more attention to the activity, recovery, and reuse of these catalysts, soon it became clear the need to deepen into the knowledge of the mechanism by which these reactions occur. Eremin and Ananikov, in a recent review, highlight the intriguing nature of these catalytic reactions, so that the mechanism knowledge is the starting point for the design of more selective and efficient catalysts. The authors stood

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34 out the various waves in these studies from the early 86
35 seventies of the twentieth century to the present: molec- 87
36 ular catalysis \longrightarrow application of nanosized catalysis 88
37 \longrightarrow the investigation of the leaching \longrightarrow concept 89
38 of “cocktail” of catalysts and recently, the dynamic nature 90
39 of the catalytic systems.¹⁷ 91

40 Among the carbon-carbon coupling reactions, the 92
41 Heck-Mizoroki (HM) reaction is the one with more 93
42 mechanism studies described in the literature until the 94
43 turn of the century.^{18–20} Most researchers have accepted 95
44 the opinion that the process is homogeneous whatever 96
45 the palladium catalyst,^{18,21} although there are some op- 97
46 posite opinions.^{22,23} In recent years, these studies have 98
47 been mainly addressed to SM reaction. For this catalytic 99
48 reaction, however, there is no consensus about the nature 100
49 of the process, contradictory results are collected 101
50 in the literature, and no conclusive proofs have been 102
51 obtained to support a heterogeneous reaction mech- 103
52 anism.¹⁸ Schmidt et col. indicate that these contradic- 104
53 tions in results and conclusions come from the contin- 105
54 uous interconversion of the species generated by the cat- 106
55 alytic precursor making ambiguous the results obtained 107
56 from the traditional homogeneity/heterogeneity tests.²⁴ 108

57 The SM reaction follow an accepted three-step process: 109
58 oxidative-addition, transmetalation and reductive 110
59 elimination. The oxidative attack of the aryl halide to 111
60 the supported Pd(0) produces its dissolution as Pd(II) 112
61 and Pd(0) species, which are responsible, in a greater or 113
62 lesser extent, of catalysis depending on the nature of the 114
63 Pd support. Dissolved palladium species undergo differ- 115
64 ent processes after leaving the catalytic cycle. Pd(II) 116
65 species can be re-adsorbed and reduced to Pd(0) on the 117
66 support. Their subsequent migration on the surface pro- 118
67 duces the growth of the previous existing Pd clusters. 119
68 A similar process is conceivable for dissolved Pd(0) 120
69 atoms, which can also end up as a part of the clusters 121
70 as a result of adsorption/superficial migration processes. 122
71 Furthermore, Pd(0) species can aggregate in solution 123
72 forming suspended colloids that can be trapped by the 124
73 support or lead to Pd black formation.^{18,25,26} 125

74 Despite this apparent simplicity, the detailed mech- 126
75 anistic study of these reactions is a difficult task that have 127
76 been developed in the last 17 years and nowadays are 128
77 still under discussion, specifically their homogeneous 129
78 or heterogeneous nature.¹⁸ The literature shows a no- 130
79 table discrepancy regarding the heterogeneous or homo- 131
80 geneous nature of the C-C cross coupling reactions.²⁴ 132
81 Nevertheless, it should be noted that this could be a 133
82 confusing terminology, as some authors consider that 134
83 “heterogeneous” catalysis is mainly driven by the Pd 135
84 atoms placed on the surface of clusters, including those 136
85 located on solubilized PdNPs,²⁷ whereas the term “ho- 137

138 mogeneous” is reserved exclusively for the catalytic ac-
139 tivity of single Pd species (atoms or complexes) in so-
140 lution. Other authors, however, consider as “heteroge-
141 neous” such processes driven by the Pd atoms located
142 on clusters anchored on the catalyst support (i.e. in-
143 solubilized Pd), while they consider as “homogeneous”
144 any process driven by the solubilized Pd species such as
145 atoms, Pd NPs, or even small Pd colloidal aggregates.
146 The later point of view has been taken in this work. In
147 this way, Jones and co-workers, in a review of 2006,
148 brought to light the difficulty of determining the true na-
149 ture of the palladium active species and distinguishing
150 between soluble vs. insoluble catalysts, molecular vs.
151 nanoparticle catalysts and with this approach, they stud-
152 ied some catalytic reactions.²⁸ Previously, Finke et col.
153 have posed these same questions for metal complexes in
154 catalytic reactions under reducing conditions.²⁹

155 In this line, several works demonstrate the heteroge-
156 neous nature of Suzuki-Miyaura C-C cross coupling re-
157 actions. Thus, Schmidt et col. conclude the essential
158 heterogeneous nature of the SM reaction for aryl bro-
159 mides when using Pd supported on activated carbon as
160 the catalyst.³⁰ They also arrived to similar conclusions
161 for Pd particles supported on MgO, silica, and Al₂O₃. In
162 these cases, the heterogeneity was proved using differ-
163 ential selectivity kinetic methods.³¹ Nevertheless, other
164 authors suggest that the Pd atoms obtained by dissolu-
165 tion of Pd NPs on the surface catalyst or the small clus-
166 ters obtained from them, are the true catalysts. Corma et
167 col. determined in C-C cross-coupling reactions that Pd
168 NPs were not the active species but small clusters, since
169 the reaction not proceed until clusters of three or four
170 palladium atoms were formed.³² Fu et col. have syn-
171 thesized robust Pd₃ clusters that exhibited a good per-
172 formance for aryl bromides.³³ In short, it is difficult
173 to determine in detail what happens during the catalytic
174 process: the identity of the catalytically active species,
175 their evolution by degradation, aggregation, dissocia-
176 tion, leaching or redeposition, or whether it is a homo-
177 geneous or heterogeneous process. Since the catalysis
178 is a kinetic phenomenon, it should be considered that
179 kinetic data can provide information about these ques-
180 tions.^{29,34}

181 The above reasons have encouraged us to synthe-
182 size a new catalyst having very small and uniformly
183 scattered Pd clusters, with the aim to test how
184 these factors influence the catalyst activity. Specifi-
185 cally, the catalyst was prepared by reduction of the
186 [Pd₂{ μ -(C₆H₄)PPh₂}₂(CH₃CN)₄](BF₄)₂ organometal-
187 lic precursor anchored on UVM-7 silica (PdNPs-UVM-
188 7). The activity of the catalyst was extensively studied
189 together with the structural and size changes of the

supported Pd domains. Both studies suggested that the catalytic activity was driven probably by dissolved Pd species. Thereby, classic tests used to distinguish between homogeneous/heterogeneous catalysis as hot-filtration, selective poisoning, and the three-phases tests were carried out. As some of these tests were inconclusive, the more specific Schmidt's analysis differential selectivity (SADS) study was carried out. SADS is a very convenient way to assess the heterogeneity of supported catalysts.^{30,35} The analysis confirmed that the catalysis was probably driven by solubilized Pd species in a great extent, which makes a difference with other Pd silica supported described in the literature.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Reagents and Materials

Commercially available 4-substitutedphenyl halides and biphenyl compounds were supplied by Aldrich. HPLC quality acetonitrile (from Baker), ethanol (from Scharlau), CH₂Cl₂ (from Baker), and hydrazine monohydrate (from Avocado) were used without further purification. UVM-7 silica (see supporting information),³⁶ and [Pd₄(μ-Br)₄{μ(C₆H₄)PPh₂}₄] **1**^{37,38} were synthesized according to procedures described in the literature.

2.2. Catalyst Synthesis

Immobilization of the Pd(II) Complex on the UVM-7 Silica (Pd(II)-UVM-7). The synthesis of UVM-7 bimodal porous silica was previously described.³⁶ In order to immobilize Pd(II) on the support, UVM-7 silica (500 mg) was partially deprotonated by reaction with 50 mL of a solution of sodium methoxide (80 mg, 1.5 mmol, in methanol); this suspension was stirred for 1 h, the solid filtered and washed several times with CH₃OH/H₂O (1:1, v/v), and finally with methanol. The white solid was dried under vacuum. Immobilization of Pd(II) compound was carried out under dry nitrogen atmosphere using Schlenk techniques through the following procedure: [Pd₂{μ-(C₆H₄)PPh₂}₂(CH₃CN)₄](BF₄)₂ was prepared by reaction of a suspension of [Pd₄(μ-Br)₄{μ(C₆H₄)PPh₂}₄] **1** (60 mg, 0.034 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂/CH₃CN (20 ml 8:1 v/v) with AgBF₄ (26 mg, 0.13 mmol). After one hour of stirring, the solution was filtered to eliminate AgBr, and poured into a suspension of partially deprotonated UVM-7 silica (500 mg) in CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL). The mixture was stirred

for 20 minutes. The yellow solid, Pd(II)-UVM-7, was filtered, washed with CH₂Cl₂ and dried under vacuum.

Synthesis of Pd NPs Supported on UVM-7 Silica (PdNPs-UVM-7). Pd(II) in Pd(II)-UVM-7 was reduced with hydrazine. The yellow solid was suspended in H₂O (40 ml), and hydrazine monohydrate (10 mL) was added dropwise at room temperature with constant stirring for 15 min. The suspension was kept stirring overnight. The resulting product was successively washed by centrifugation with H₂O, CH₃OH:H₂O (1:1 v/v) and CH₂Cl₂. The grey solid, PdNPs-UVM-7, was air dried. The wash by centrifugation avoided the loss of Pd NPs observed by filtration.

[PdCl₂(CH₃CN)₂]. A solution of [PdCl₂(CH₃CN)₂] 0.03 M was obtained solving 51 mg (0.3 mmol) of PdCl₂ in 10 mL of CH₃CN.

2.3. Instruments

Characterization of Materials. The Pd contents were determined by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analysis using a scanning electron microscope (Philips - SEM-XL 30). For electron microscopy analyses, the samples were dispersed in ethanol and placed onto a carbon coated copper microgrid and left to dry before observation. The TEM and HRTEM microstructural characterizations were carried out using a JEOL JEM-1010 instrument operating at 100 kV and equipped with a CCD camera and a Tecnai G2 F20(FI) instrument, respectively. STEM-HAADF images were acquired on a JEOL-2100F microscope operated at 200 kV. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with monochromatic Cu Kα source operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. Patterns were collected in steps of 0.02° (2α) over the angular range 1-10.0° (2α), with an acquisition time of 25 s per step. Additionally, XRD patterns were recorded over a wider angular range, 10-80°, (2α) to determine the presence of segregated crystalline phases. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were recorded in an automated Micromeritics ASAP2020 instrument. Prior to the adsorption measurements, the samples were outgassed in situ in vacuum (10⁻⁶ Torr) at 120 °C for 15 hours to remove adsorbed gases.

Kinetic Study. HPLC measurements were carried out using a chromatograph (JASCO) equipped with an analog-digital converter unit (Jasco LC-Net II), quaternary gradient pump (PU-2089), diode array detector (MD-2018), column oven (Jasco co-2065 Plus), and manual injector (Reodhyne 720i). Reverse-phase C-18 column (100×4.6 mm, stationary phase 2.6 μm fused core silica C-18 particles, from Phenomenex) was

235 mounted in series with a column guard (AJO-8768 C- 286
236 18). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded at 298K with a 287
237 Bruker 400 and a 500 AMX spectrometers. Samples 288
238 were dissolved in CDCl₃ or CD₂Cl₂ and chemical shifts 289
239 (δ in ppm) were referred to Si(CH₃)₄. 290

240 *Schmidt's Analysis of Differential Selectivity* 291
241 (*SADS*). Analysis were followed by means of GC 292
242 because the SM reaction products could not be re- 293
243 solved adequately using HPLC. Chromatographic 294
244 separations were carried out using an Agilent 6890+ 295
245 gas chromatograph equipped with a FID detector and 296
246 polimetilsiloxane HP-1 column. Initially, the oven 297
247 temperature was set to 50 °C, which was raised up 298
248 to 200 °C at 70 °C/min. The final temperature was 299
249 maintained for 8 min. Injector and FID temperatures 300
250 were set to 250 °C and 230 °C respectively. No other 301
251 products different from the biphenylic derivatives were 302
252 observed. 303

253 2.4. Kinetic Experiments 304

254 *HPLC Calibration and Analysis Procedures.* Chrom- 305
255 atographic standards were prepared by diluting 306
256 with CH₃CN stock solutions containing the 4- 307
257 substitutedphenyl halide (10⁻² M) and its reaction prod- 308
258 uct (0.5 – 1.0 × 10⁻² M) in CH₃CN. The chromato- 309
259 graphic separation of the reaction samples was carried 310
260 out passing as the eluent a solution of CH₃CN (0.25% 311
261 v/v in CF₃COOH) and H₂O in a ratio 65:35 v/v through 312
262 a C-18 reverse phase column thermostated at 30 °C at 313
263 a rate flow of 1.5 mL min⁻¹. Concentration of reac- 314
264 tants and products was calculated from the response fac- 315
265 tors, which were estimated from calibration of the ap- 316
266 propriate standards with the exception of phenylboronic 317
267 acid, as calibration proved not to be quantitative under 318
268 the HPLC conditions required to resolve the 4- 319
269 substitutedphenyl halide/biphenyl mixtures. No other 320
270 products different from the biphenylic derivatives were 321
271 observed. 322

272 *GC Calibration and Analysis Procedures.* Chromato- 323
273 graphic standards were prepared from separated stock 324
274 solutions of the aryl halide (0.5 mmol) and its cor- 325
275 responding SM biphenylic derivative (0.5 mmol) dis- 326
276 solved in ethanol (25 mL) using 4,4'-dimethylbiphenyl 327
277 as internal standard. Standards were analyzed according 328
278 to the GC method previously described, and concentra- 329
279 tion of reactants and products was calculated from the 330
280 response factors estimated from calibration. 331

281 *General Procedure to Study the Kinetics of Suzuki-* 332
282 *Miyaura Reactions.* In a typical experiment, the 4- 333
283 substitutedphenyl halide (0.5 mmol), phenylboronic 334
284 acid (0.75 mmol), K₂CO₃ (0.75 mmol), and ethanol 335
285 (50 mL, 96% v/v) were introduced into a 2-neck flask 336

equipped with a cooler and a thermostat jacket attached
to a water bath. After heating at 80 °C, a sample of 0.25
mL was extracted (the blank) and the catalyst added typi-
cally in 1 mol % with respect to the 4-substitutedphenyl
halide (32.8 mg, 5 × 10⁻³ mmol of Pd). The progress
of the reaction was monitored taking aliquots (0.25 mL)
at regular time intervals. After extraction, aliquots were
poured into vials containing 0.25 mL of HCl (0.15 M)
as a quencher. Then, CH₃CN (0.5 mL) was added, the
solution filtered with a 0.02 μm pore size microfilter
(from Whatman), and the volume adjusted to 10 mL
with more CH₃CN. Portions of 20 μm of these solu-
tions were analyzed according to the HPLC procedure
described above.

Study of Catalyst Activity. The kinetics of SM reac-
tion along the reusing cycles of the catalyst was carried
out following the general procedure using 1-bromo-4-
nitrobenzene as the substrate. After reaction completion
(90 min), the catalyst was separated by centrifugation,
washed with ethanol, and dried at 90 °C for 24 hours.
The recycled catalyst was added to a new reaction mix-
ture containing the usual concentrations of reactants, but
adding a half of the usual K₂CO₃ amount (50 mg, 0.40
mmol). The process was repeated until a total of 7 cy-
cles were completed. The recycled catalyst was char-
acterized for selected cycles by TEM-HAADF to check
the dispersion and size of Pd nanoclusters. Furthermore,
N₂ adsorption isotherms were measured with the aim to
check the integrity of the UVM-7 silica pore systems
among cycles.

SADS Studies. The differential selectivity analy-
sis was carried out for the systems: 4-bromo-anisole/
4-bromo-acetophenone, 4-bromo-toluene/ 4-bromo-
anisole, 4-iodo-anisole/ 4-iodo-acetophenone, and 4-
iodo-anisole/4-iodotoluene. The activity of Pd NPs-
UVM-7 was compared to that of [PdCl₂(CNCH₃)₂]
as homogeneous catalyst. In a typical experiment,
two aryl halides (0.50 mmol of each one), phenyl-
boronic acid (1.5 mmol) were dissolved in 100 mL of
ethanol (96% v/v). 50 or 25 mL of this solution were
introduced in both reactors having their thermostatic
jackets connected in series and K₂CO₃ (0.75 or 0.38
mmol) were respectively added. When the mixtures
reached 80 °C, the solid catalyst (0.5%, 5 × 10⁻³ mmol,
[Pd]=1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M) or a freshly prepared solution of
[PdCl₂(CNCH₃)₂] (6.0 × 10⁻⁴ mmol, [Pd]=2.4 × 10⁻⁵
M) were respectively added. The kinetics were fol-
lowed for 240 min according to the method previously
described. The aliquots extracted from reactors were fil-
tered, cooled to -4°C, and analyzed by GC according to
the method described above.

2.5. Investigation of the Homogeneous vs. Heterogeneous Nature of Catalysis

Hot Filtering Test. 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene (102.4 mg, 0.51 mmol), phenylboronic acid (92.7 mg, 76 mmol), K_2CO_3 (104 mg, 0.75 mmol), catalyst (11.6 mg, 2.47×10^{-3} mmol of Pd), and ethanol (50 mL, 96% v/v) were allowed to react at 80 °C for 4 min. Then, 20 mL of reaction mixture were filtered with a 0.02 μ m pore size microfilter, poured into a bottom flask maintained at the work temperature, and the reaction allowed continuing in the filtrate for 60 min. The progress of reaction before and after filtration was determined by HPLC.

Centrifugation Test. A reaction mixture was prepared according to the procedure described for the hot filtering test, and allowed progressing for 2 minutes. Then, 20 mL of the reactive mixture were centrifuged, and the supernatant liquid transferred to a bottom flask maintained at the work temperature. The progress of the reaction in both the filtrate and the original mixture was monitored by HPLC.

Catalyst Poisoning. 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene (0.5 mmol), phenylboronic acid (0.75 mmol), K_2CO_3 (0.75 mmol), ethanol (50 mL, 96% v/v), and the catalyst (12.2 mg, 2.6×10^{-3} mmol of Pd) were introduced into a reaction flask. In a first experiment, 3-mercaptopropyl silicagel (100 mg) were added at the beginning of the reaction. In a second run, QuadraPure TU (100 mg) was added after 4 min of reaction. The progress of the reaction was monitored by HPLC.³⁹

Three Phases Test. The three phase test was carried out analogously to the procedure published by Cruden et al.,⁴⁰ Kantam et col.,⁴¹ and Gruber-Woelfler.⁴² Amino functionalized silicagel (BrPhCONH-SiO₂) was synthesized according to the method described in the literature.^{41,42} The test was carried out following the reaction conditions described in the general procedure using as 4-substitutedphenyl halides 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene and 1-bromo-4-amidobenzene, the last supported on silica. After completion, the solid was separated by filtration, and washed with ethanol and CH_2Cl_2 . The solid was hydrolyzed following the procedure described in the literature.⁴¹ 4-bromobenzoic acid and [1,1'-biphenyl]-4-carboxylic acid obtained were analyzed by ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

3. METHODOLOGY OF ANALYSIS OF KINETIC DATA

The reaction order respect to the catalyst and phenylboronic acid was determined applying the initial rate method, according to the procedure described in the

supporting information. The orders calculated at $t = 0$ were corroborated by integral methods fitting the data to Eq. (1),

$$F_{11}(x) = \ln \left(\frac{x+c}{x(1+c)} \right) = k[A]_0 t \quad (1)$$

with $x = [A]/[A]_0$, and $c = [B]_0/[A]_0 - 1$, where A and B stand for the 4-substitutedphenyl halide and phenylboronic acid. Eq. (1) is the integrated form of the ordinary differential equation system shown in Eq. (2),

$$-\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{d[B]}{dt} = k[A][B] \quad (2)$$

which described adequately most kinetic runs, especially those involving the very active nitro or aceto derivatives of 4-substitutedphenyl halides. Nevertheless, the data analysis of systems presenting loss of catalyst activity along time was carried out by fitting the concentration curves to the differential Eq. (3),

$$-\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{d[B]}{dt} = k(t)[A][B] \quad (3)$$

where,

$$k(t) = \frac{k_0 + c_1 t}{1 + c_2 t} \quad (4)$$

The empirical relationship displayed in Eq.(4) considers that catalyst activity changes along time, and it provides the initial (k_0), and infinity-time ($k_\infty = c_1/c_2$) catalyst performance. Concentration-time profiles estimated from Eqs. (3)-(4) were calculated by numerical integration using the OPKMCR facilities, a specialized software for kinetic data analysis written in the Julia programming language,⁴³ developed in our laboratory.

In order to compare the kinetic results with those found in the literature, the catalyst activity was estimated from the turn over frequency at zero time (TOF₀) calculated according to Eq.(5),

$$TOF_0 = \frac{r_0}{[Pd]} = \frac{k_0[A][B]}{[Pd]} \quad (5)$$

and from the catalytic constant defined by Eq. (6),

$$k_{cat} = \frac{k_0}{[Pd]} \quad (6)$$

where r_0 , $[A]_0$, $[B]_0$ and $[Pd]$ were the initial rate, initial concentrations of 4-substitutedphenyl halide and phenylboronic acid, and the total concentration of palladium inside the reactor.

Scheme 1: Synthesis procedure of PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst. i) Partial deprotonation of UVM-7. ii) Synthesis of the cationic complex **2**. iii) Immobilization of the Pd(II) complex on UVM-7 silica. iv) Reduction of Pd(II)-UVM-7 with hydrazine giving the catalyst, PdNPs-UVM-7.

Table 1: Surface (s)^a, volume (v)^b, and diameter (d)^b pore for UVM-7 and PdNPs-UVM-7 measured after the first and 7th cycles of reusing catalyst kinetics.

silica	small pore ^d			large pore ^e	
	s/m ² g ⁻¹	v/m ³ g ⁻¹	d/nm	v/m ³ g ⁻¹	d/nm
UVM-7	1105	0.98	3.02	1.41	49.0
^c before reaction	582	0.34	2.59	1.05	45.6
cycle 1 ^c	340	0.17	2.60	0.52	47.2
cycle 3 ^c	183	0.10	-	0.52	41.8
cycle 7 ^c	147	0.10	-	0.5	39.8

^a Surface calculated according to BET model; ^b diameter and volume pore calculated according to BJH model; ^c PdNPs-UVM-7.; ^d

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Catalyst Synthesis and Characterization

Catalyst synthesis. Since silanol groups were the anchoring sites connecting the Pd-organometallic precursor of Pd NPs, they were deprotonated previously to the incorporation of complexes to the UVM-7 silica, as the surfactant evolution was realized by calcination this leading to a relatively low proportion of silanol groups. The calcined UVM-7 silica was preferred as support to the extracted one because it degraded less in the basic medium provided by K₂CO₃.

Scheme 1 summarizes the synthesis procedure. The solvated complex [Pd₂{μ-(C₆H₄)PPh₂}₂(CH₃CN)₄](BF₄)₂ **2** was immobilized on UVM-7 silica by reaction with the

deprotonated silanol groups in CH₂Cl₂ containing some drops of CH₃CN. The acetonitrile molecules were easily replaced, and the palladium compound was immobilized by ionic interaction between the complex **2** and the anionic Si-O⁻ sites, giving the solid labeled as Pd(II)-UVM-7. Its subsequent reduction with hydrazine led to the heterogeneous PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst as a gray solid, although sometimes it appeared black due to Ag contamination. Thereby, the solid was exhaustively washed (Si/Ag molar ratio > 200). In any case, it was checked that silver was not involved in the catalytic processes.

This strategy of synthesis allowed for anchoring directly the dinuclear Pd-organometallic complex without using intermediate species, as for example silanes containing terminal carboxylate moieties. In this way, we

Figure 1: Representative TEM (a) and STEM-HAADF (b) images of the PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst before used. The schematic model of the UVM-7 architecture and the Pd NPs size histogram are showed in the insets.

reduced the number of preparative steps, the cost and, additionally, we preserved a larger volume of empty pores to incorporate the complex. Furthermore, this methodology, which combines the use of dimeric Pd(II) complexes as Pd NPs precursors together with an homogeneous distribution of deprotonated silanol groups on the silica, enabled a large dispersion of the Pd NPs on the UVM-7 silica.

Catalyst Characterization. The amount of palladium immobilized on silica was determined by scanning electron microscopy with a dispersive detector of X-ray energies. We obtained a value of real Si/Pd molar ratio of 100 ± 5 averaged from data corresponding to ca. 50 different particles. The low standard deviations achieved confirmed that the catalyst was chemically ho-

441 mogeneous at micrometric scale with a regular disper-
 442 sion of Pd and Si atoms throughout the inorganic walls.
 443 The high chemical homogeneity was due to an homoge-
 444 neous activation of the silica surface, and the use of an
 445 organometallic Pd complex precursor. In a cooperative
 446 way, both factors hindered the segregation through coa-
 447 lescence of Pd species. The Pd content in the final cat-
 448 alyst was significantly higher than that expected from
 449 the amount of reagents used (Si/Pd= 180). This rela-
 450 tive enrichment in Pd was due to the partial solubility
 451 of the silica support that occurred during the thoroughly
 452 washing and, in addition, confirmed the effectiveness of
 453 hydrazine as reducing agent under our working condi-
 454 tions. This fact was consistent with the practically ab-
 455 sence of P atoms derived from the phosphine ligands
 456 (Si/P= 258).

457 A representative TEM image of PdNPs-UVM-7 be-
 458 fore used is shown in Figure 1(a). The catalyst mor-
 459 phology can be described as being formed by assembled
 460 primary mesoporous nanoparticles defining a second
 461 macroporous system of textural type. We can observe
 462 very small dark spots that must correspond to Pd NPs.
 463 Thereby, the incorporation of complex **2** and the subse-
 464 quent chemical reduction did not alter the typical UVM-
 465 7 architecture from a qualitative point of view. Among
 466 the different mesoporous materials available, the UVM-
 467 7 silica was selected for complex **2** immobilization in-
 468 stead of the conventional MCM-41. The ordered 1-D
 469 mesoporous system of the MCM-41 silica can present
 470 problems of accessibility. This handicap is more pro-
 471 nounced when the size of the species to be incorporate
 472 is relatively large, as in the case of complex **2**. In fact,
 473 we expected that species **2** were anchored preferably on
 474 the external surface of the nanoparticle and in the meso-
 475 pore entrances. If we use silica MCM-41, which usually
 476 has a micrometric particle size, it necessarily implies the
 477 presence of mesopores with micrometric length.

478 As previously mentioned, a restricted diffusion of
 479 complex **2** along the mesopores, and even a certain pore
 480 blocking, cannot be discarded. In this case, a large pro-
 481 portion of the total silica surface would result wasted.
 482 To avoid this issue, an alternative was to reduce the par-
 483 ticle size in the range of microns to nanometers. In this
 484 sense, UVM-7 silica can be considered as a nanometric
 485 version of the MCM-41 material. In order to accurately
 486 observe the presence and average size of the Pd NPs, we
 487 recorded a STEM-HAADF image of the PdNPs-UVM-
 488 7 catalyst (see Figure 1(b)). This image showed a very
 489 good dispersion of Pd nanoparticles, seen as bright spots
 490 throughout the mass of the silica. Moreover, our method
 491 led to small Pd NPs (ca. 2.5 nm) with a narrow particle
 492 size distribution.

493 The XRD pattern of PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst pre-
 494 served the intense peak and the small shoulder in the
 495 low-angle domain characteristic of the UVM-7 silica
 496 (see Figure S1, see supporting information), that can
 497 be associated to the (100) and the overlapped (110) and
 498 (200) reflections of a MCM-41-like hexagonal cell, re-
 499 spectively. These signals indicated the existence of a
 500 partially ordered mesostructure according to TEM im-
 501 ages. The lower resolution and intensity of the diffrac-
 502 tion peaks, when compared to the diffractogram of a
 503 UVM-7 pure silica, indicated a certain loss of order.
 504 This fact could be due to the contrast loss associated
 505 with the incorporation of PdNPs inside the mesopores,
 506 and also to a certain degradation degree that could occur
 507 during the reduction with hydrazine, which generated a
 508 moderately basic pH. On the other hand, the absence
 509 of signals in the high-angle regime was also consistent
 510 with the small size of the Pd NPs determined through
 511 STEM-HAADF.

512 The N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms of the
 513 PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst are shown in Figure S2. In-
 514 corporation of Pd on the UVM-7 silica induced a sig-
 515 nificant loss of BET area and pore volume when com-
 516 pared to the pure silica, see Table 1. This evolution
 517 was attributed to three factors: the incorporation of Pd,
 518 which increased the mass of the material, and it could
 519 block the mesopores in a certain proportion, and the
 520 partial degradation suffered during the treatment with
 521 hydrazine. The preserved surface area of the PdNPs-
 522 UVM-7 solid corresponded to a large extent to the ex-
 523 ternal area associated to the large inter-particle pores
 524 that usually is around 180-200 m²/g. The remaining
 525 surface up to 582 m²/g must correspond to intraparticle
 526 unblocked or partially collapsed mesopores. Thus, the
 527 incorporation/generation of Pd NPs led to a reduction
 528 in the intraparticle mesopore size. However, the tex-
 529 tural type interparticle macroporous system maintained
 530 its size and a large part of its original volume. Hence,
 531 this large and accessible pore system is truly the envi-
 532 ronment where the active Pd NPs reside.

533 4.2. Kinetic Study

534 The PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst has been tested in the
 535 SM reaction using different the 4-substitutedphenyl
 536 halides shown in Scheme 2.

537 *Catalyst activity.* The synthesis of the Pd NPs sup-
 538 ported on UVM-7 silica from organometallic precur-
 539 sors is a time-consuming process. Thereby, it is worth
 540 considering whether this approach improves the cat-
 541 alyst activity. This property was checked for the 4-
 542 substitutedphenyl halides listed in Table 2. All reac-
 543 tions were carried out under the same experimental con-

Scheme 2: Suzuki-Miyaura reaction

544 ditions, typically [4-substitutedphenyl halide] = 0.01
 545 M, [PhB(OH)₂] = 0.015 M, and [Pd] = 10⁻⁴ mol/L in
 546 EtOH:H₂O 96:4 v/v.

547 The results collected in the supporting information
 548 (tables S1 and S2, and figures S3 and S4) indicated that
 549 the reaction was first-order respect to Pd. The least-
 550 squares fitting to Eqs.(1) and (2) also showed that the
 551 rate law was first-order respect to the aryl halide and
 552 phenyl boronic acid concentrations for the faster re-
 553 acting systems, i.e., 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene, 1-iodo-4-
 554 nitrobenzene, and 1-iodo-4-acetobenzene. The slower
 555 reacting aryl halides, however, apparently exhibited a
 556 different kinetic law.

557 The change in the rate law could be explained argu-
 558 ing that the several aryl halides react through different
 559 reaction mechanisms. However, a more satisfactory ex-
 560 planation is related to the dynamic nature of the dis-
 561 tribution of Pd species during cross-coupling reactions.
 562 Thus, when a SM reaction reaches a critical tempera-
 563 ture, the aryl halides interact with Pd clusters.⁴⁴ This
 564 interaction produces a partial dissolution of Pd(II) and
 565 Pd(0) species that subsequently suffer several equilibria
 566 (aggregation, re-precipitation) responsible of the exis-
 567 tence of Pd species in various aggregation states. Ob-
 568 viously, the temporal evolution of the Pd distribution
 569 species modifies the overall activity of the catalyst.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸

If we call k_i to the rate coefficient of the process cat-
 570 alyzed by the Pd_i species (e.g. Pd atoms in solution,
 571 solubilized aggregates of different size, anchored clus-
 572 ters on the support, solubilized Pd molecular species, all
 573 of them with different activities), we can write, assum-
 574 ing first-order for the substrate and phenyl boronic acid,
 575 the rate the expression shown in Eq. (7),

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{d[A]}{dt} &= \left(\sum_i k_i [\text{Pd}_i] \right) [A][B] = \\
 &= \left(\sum_i k_i X_i \right) [\text{Pd}][A][B] = k(t)[A][B] \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

576 where [Pd] is the overall concentration of Pd provided
 577 by the catalyst, and X_i the mole fraction of Pd i-th-
 578 species. The term between parentheses depends on the

Table 2: Kinetic and statistical fitting parameters for the SM reaction with B(OH)₂Ph for the studied 4-substitutedphenyl halides (X-C₆H₄-R).^a

X	R	$k_0 / \text{min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$	$k_\infty / \text{min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$	$k_{cat} \times 10^{-5} / \text{min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-2}$	TOF $\times 10^{-3} / \text{h}^{-1}$	$\eta(24\text{h})^b$	R	LOF(%) ^c
I	CH ₃	27.8	0.2	2.77	2.8	97	0.9991	2.1
	OCH ₃	32.4	0.3	3.24	2.9	98	0.997	3.0
	H	32.3	0.07	3.19	2.9	96	0.996	4.2
	COCH ₃	151	-	15.1	14.4	99	0.9996	1.8
	NO ₂	162	-	16.1	14.7	99	0.998	4.4
Br	CH ₃	2.7	0	0.27	0.28	10	0.996	5.6
	OCH ₃	1.7	0	0.17	0.17	16	0.997	5.3
	H	0.6	0	0.06	0.06	34	0.98	12.1
	COCH ₃	6.6	0	0.65	0.59	90	0.998	2.5
	NO ₂	17.0	-	1.71	1.55	99	0.994	6.0
Cl	NO ₂	0.78	0	0.08	0.07	< 5	0.9996	1.8

^a In all kinetic runs: [Pd] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol/L; ^b η : reaction yield; ^c LOF: lack of fit in %.

573 Pd species distribution, which in turn varies with time
574 owed to the complex Pd species interconversion equi-
575 libria established in the reactor.

576 As quantification of Pd in the different aggregates is
577 unknown, coefficients k_i cannot be determined. Nev-
578 ertheless, the shape of $k(t)$ can be deduced by fitting
579 the concentration data to an empirical function. In this
580 work, the sigmoidal empirical function shown in Eq. (4)
581 has been used. Although the coefficients of this expres-
582 sion have not chemical meaning, it is possible to extract
583 information about the initial (k_0) and infinite time (k_∞)
584 behavior of the reactive system.

585 Figure 2 shows two different behaviors concerning
586 the conversion of substrates. On the one hand, the
587 conversion-time profiles of the most active 4-substituted
588 halides (R=NO₂ X=I, Br; R=COCH₃, X=I) were cor-
589 rectly predicted by Eq.(2). In this case, the reaction
590 reached its completion before 5 min.

591 However, the less active substrates deviated markedly
592 from this model, yielding conversions below the unity
593 even after 24h. For these substrates, the reaction rate
594 slowed down significantly, suggesting a progressive de-
595 activation of the catalyst. Accordingly, data from these
596 systems were analyzed using Eq.(3) that included the
597 empirical relationship (4), which took into account the
598 change in the Pd species distribution with time. The
599 second-order rate constants at zero (k_0) and infinity time
600 (k_∞), statistical coefficients, and catalyst activity are
601 summarized in Table 2. It is worth noting that the re-
602 action rate for the more reactive aryl halides is high
603 enough to make $k(t)$ independent of time (i.e., domi-
604 nated by k_0), which makes the rate law in Eq.(2) to be
605 fulfilled, whereas this parameter is comparable to the
606 rate of interconversion processes for the less reactive
607 aryl halides, making these reactions to deviate from the

Figure 2: Conversion (expressed in times one) vs. time profiles for (a) iodobenzene, and (b) bromobenzene derivatives listed in Table 2; R= (Δ) NO₂, (\square) COCH₃, (\square) H, (\circ) CH₃, (\bullet) OCH₃. **Insets:** Relative variation of the second-order rate coefficient ($k(t)/k_0$) with time calculated from Eq.(4).

608 simple rate law given by Eqs.(1) and (2).

609 Transmetalation is believed to be the rate-
610 determining step in most SM couplings.⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ As this
611 step involves the nucleophilic attack of $[\text{B}(\text{OH})_3\text{Ph}]^-$

612 to the Pd atom of $[\text{Pd}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{R})]$ intermediate 664
613 (see Scheme S1), the reaction rate was expected to 665
614 increase with increasing the electron-withdrawing 666
615 nature of the 4-substitutedphenyl halide substituents, 667
616 R, for substrates sharing the same halogen. On 668
617 the other hand, the oxidative addition is usually an 669
618 equilibrium step that is so much more displaced 670
619 towards the formation of $[\text{PdX}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{R})]$ (X=I, Br, 671
620 Cl) as the weaker the C-X bond is. The concen- 672
621 tration profiles shown in Figure 2 clearly show that 673
622 4-substitutedphenyl iodides reacted faster than their 674
623 corresponding bromo or chloro derivatives. Assuming 675
624 identical Pd catalyst charges, the kinetic coefficients 676
625 collected in Table 2 reflect the above observation. For 677
626 example, the more active 1-iodo-4-nitro-iodobenzene 678
627 reacted 10 times faster than 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene 679
628 ($k_{cat,I}/k_{cat,Br} = 9.4$), the less active 1-iodo-4-methyl- 680
629 benzene exhibited the same ratio of activity respect to 681
630 1-bromo-4-methyl-benzene ($k_{cat,I}/k_{cat,Br} = 9.5$), and 682
631 1-chloro-4-nitro-benzene barely reacted compared 683
632 to 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene ($k_{cat,Cl}/k_{cat,Br} = 0.05$) or 684
633 1-iodo-4-nitrobenzene ($k_{cat,Cl}/k_{cat,I} = 0.005$). For 4- 685
634 substitutedphenyl halides having the same halogen, 686
635 the influence of the electron-withdrawing nature of 687
636 substituents was as expected. 4-substitutedphenyl 688
637 iodides having electron-withdrawing groups (R=NO₂, 689
638 COCH₃) reacted roughly 5-6 times faster than those 690
639 with electron-donor substituents (R=CH₃, OCH₃, H). 691
640 Identical trend was observed for aryl bromides. 692

641 It is important to note that conversion-time curves 693
642 were indicative of changes in the Pd distribution 694
643 species. Figure 2(a) shows that the 4-substitutedphenyl 695
644 iodides with R=NO₂, COCH₃ were quantitatively con- 696
645 verted into their biphenyl products in about 3-4 min, 697
646 while those with R=CH₃, H, OCH₃ barely reached con- 698
647 versions of 0.8 after 100 min. More remarkable are the 699
648 insets of Figure 2, which show that the relative second- 700
649 order rate constant ($k(t)/k_0$) calculated from Eq.(4) 701
650 dropped more than 80% during the first 10 min., and 702
651 only 15% of the initial activity was maintained after 25 703
652 min. 4-substitutedphenyl bromides presented a similar 704
653 trend, but now all systems suffered deactivation, with 705
654 the exception of 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene. 706

655 At this point, it is worth considering whether the pro- 707
656 posed synthetic approach leads to a really active cat- 708
657 alyst. Thereby, the activity must be compared with 709
658 that of other systems. In order to compare properly 710
659 the activity, the k_{cat} and TOF values should be used, 711
660 as other parameters, e.g. conversion or yield, are not 712
661 significant enough if the initial conditions of kinetic 713
662 runs are not provided. As far as we know, k_{cat} val- 714
663 ues for the SM reaction have not been reported. For- 715

664 tunately, Pérez-Leyva et col.³² have reported the TOF₀ 716
665 values (initial turn over frequency) for the Suzuki re- 717
666 action of iodobenzene ($3.20 \times 10^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$) and bromoben- 718
667 zene ($7.60 \times 10^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$) with phenylboronic acid cat- 719
668 alyzed by extremely small Pd nanoclusters (3-4 atoms 720
669 of Pd), together with the initial conditions of the ex- 721
670 periments. Therein, Pd NPs were stabilized in N- 722
671 methylpyrrolidone/water medium at 130 °C. Interest- 723
672 ingly, the authors found that the activity of bromoben- 724
673 zene was higher than that of iodobenzene, which is un- 725
674 usual for a SM reaction. From the above information, 726
675 the values of k_{cat} could be estimated for iodobenzene 727
676 ($4.0 \times 10^2 \text{ min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-2}$) and bromobenzene (9.5×10^2 728
677 $\text{min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-2}$). On the other hand, Table 2 shows the ac- 729
678 tivity of the catalyst, prepared from the organometallic 730
679 precursor, against iodobenzene (TOF₀=2900 h^{-1} , $k_{cat} =$ 731
680 $3.2 \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-2}$), and bromobenzene (TOF₀= 60 732
681 h^{-1} , $k_{cat} = 6 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}\text{M}^{-2}$). The k_{cat} values were 733
682 higher, and slightly higher, for iodobenzene and bro- 734
683 mbenzene when compared with those estimated from 735
684 Prez-Leyva's publication, suggesting that the catalyst 736
685 synthesized in this work was initially as active as the 737
686 stabilized Pd nanoclusters in solution. Furthermore, Fu 738
687 et col.³³ have synthesized Pd₃ clusters and they have 739
688 measured the TOF (in h^{-1}) for bromobenzene (2450 740
689 vs. 60 this work), 4-bromotoluene (2390 vs. 280), 741
690 4-bromoanisole (2440 vs. 170), 4-bromonitrobenzene 742
691 (1160 vs. 590), and 1-bromo-4-nitro-benzene (1170 vs. 743
692 1550). Fu clusters are more active for the less acti- 744
693 vate aryl halide, having similar activity for 1-bromo-4- 745
694 nitro-benzene. Interestingly, the reactivity order of aryl 746
695 halides is reversed, which is explained by the authors 747
696 assuming a reaction mechanism different from that gen- 748
697 erally accepted for the SM reaction. 749

700 The kinetic measurements indicate that the catalyst 701
702 activity decreases with time, especially for the less ac- 703
704 tive aryl halides, suggesting that the distribution of Pd 704
705 species changes notably along the reaction. As the value 705
706 of $k(t)$ depends on the reactivity of the several aggre- 706
707 gates and their relative mass distribution, kinetic data 707
708 concurs with formation of less active Pd species during 708
709 the reaction. 709

710 At this point, the key issue is to elucidate how the sol- 710
711 ule and supported Pd contribute to catalytic process. 711
712 Obviously, kinetic measurements alone do not allow to 712
713 specify what species, soluble or supported, drive the 713
714 catalysis. Nevertheless, the literature suggests that sol- 714
715 ubilized Pd in form of atoms, Pd molecular species, or 715
716 very small clusters are the more active, even at very low 716
717 concentration.³² In fact, most synthetic SMR described 717
718 in the literature using the homogeneous Pd(AcO)₂ cat- 718
719 alyst proceed at room temperature, while SMR per- 719

Table 3: Kinetic and statistical fitting parameters to Eq.(1) for the SM reaction of 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene with phenylboronic acid for the diverse reusing cycles of catalyst (n).^a

n	$[A]_0 \times 10^2 / \text{M}$	c	$k_{cat} \times 10^{-4} / \text{min}^{-1} \text{M}^{-2}$	$\text{TOF}_0 \times 10^{-3} / \text{h}^{-1}$
1	1.02	0.49	17.4	1.70
2	1.03	0.50	2.67	0.27
3	1.02	0.51	1.23	0.17
4	1.02	0.50	1.15	0.11
5	1.01	0.51	0.89	0.06
6	1.01	0.49	0.37	0.02
7	1.01	0.52	0.16	0.01

^a $[\text{Pd}] = 1.01 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; $T = 80^\circ\text{C}$.

716 formed with supported catalysts need temperatures in 754
 717 the range 100-130 °C. This sounds reasonable as the 755
 718 larger the particle is, the lesser is the number of avail- 756
 719 able superficial Pd atoms. Furthermore, reactions on 757
 720 supported clusters usually are delayed due to diffusive 758
 721 effects. 759

722 The information gathered from the kinetic experi- 760
 723 ments could be explained from the working hypothesis 761
 724 presented below. In the course of the synthesis, very 762
 725 small supported Pd clusters are formed due to the mild 763
 726 conditions of the reduction of the disperse dinuclear 764
 727 Pd(II) complexes anchored on the UVM-7 silica. The 765
 728 existence of these clusters does not exclude that a cer- 766
 729 tain amount of Pd is dispersed in form of small Pd NPs 767
 730 or even as atomic Pd. After heating the reaction mix- 768
 731 ture, Pd dissolves as a consequence two processes. The 769
 732 first involves the attack of aryl halides to the Pd atoms 770
 733 on the support when the temperature reaches a critical 771
 734 value at which the C-halogen bond is activated. Never- 772
 735 theless, it is conceivable a second process in which the 773
 736 Pd fraction formed by adsorbed atoms and Pd NPs is 774
 737 partially dissolved without the intervention of the aryl 775
 738 halide. The latter mechanism is proposed as Pd should 776
 739 be quickly solubilized to explain the maximum value of 777
 740 $k(t)$ at the beginning of the reaction, see the insets in 778
 741 Figure 2. 779

742 It is worth to note at this point that the method used 780
 743 for the synthesis of the catalyst makes a difference re- 781
 744 spect to the Pd solubility. For example, classic methods 782
 745 based on the impregnation of silica with Pd (II) com- 783
 746 plexes ($\text{Pd}(\text{AcO})_2$ or PdCl_2) followed by drastic reduc- 784
 747 tion conditions (H_2 at high temperature or refluxing in 785
 748 methanol) led to larger Pd domains for which the second 786
 749 solubilization mechanism is probably operative only in 787
 750 a lesser extent. 788

751 If it is admitted that the dissolved Pd (atoms, small 789
 752 NPs) is more active than the supported one, the first 790
 753 species will be responsible for most of the substrate 791

conversion at the beginning of the reaction.^{45,46} At this
 point, the conversion rate is controlled by the k_0 coeffi-
 cient. For the most reactive 4-substituted phenyl halides,
 the conversion takes place at a higher rate than that re-
 lated to the aggregation/redeposition processes. Once
 the concentration of the substrate has decreased suffi-
 ciently, the soluble Pd suffer the admitted aggregation
 and processes, originating larger but less active Pd su-
 perficial clusters or colloidal aggregates.⁵² This phe-
 nomenon has not kinetic consequences as it takes place
 by the end of reaction, and thus no appreciable change
 of the rate constant is observed. However, if the sub-
 strate has little affinity for the catalyst, the dissolved Pd
 species will not be involved all the time with the sub-
 strate. As a result, the metal form larger aggregates,
 which is reflected in the continuously decreasing values
 of $k(t)$ with time. Finally, the activity of the catalyst sta-
 bilizes by the end of the reaction, being described by the
 k_∞ coefficient. At this stage, the low $k(t)$ values indicate
 that the catalysis is mainly driven by the less active Pd
 species, probably insolubilized Pd and the larger aggre-
 gates in solution.

Reusing Catalyst Experiments. From the above,
 it is conceivable that the catalyst prepared from the
 organometallic precursor contains adsorbed a certain
 amount of potentially soluble Pd that provides a high
 reactivity at the beginning of the reaction. If this Pd
 aggregates and precipitates on the support as larger Pd
 clusters when the system cools down, the reuse of the
 catalyst over a series of cycles must induce a strong de-
 crease of activity between cycles. In contrast, if the
 insolubilized Pd drives mainly the catalysis, this phe-
 nomenon should not be observed, or if do, in a lesser
 extent. A series of reusing cycles of the catalyst was
 analyzed to verify the above hypothesis.

Figure 3 shows the values of $F_{11}(x)$, see Eq.(1), for a
 number of reactions (cycles) in which the catalyst was
 reused. For the first cycle, the function behaved linearly

Figure 3: $F_{11}(x)$ vs. time plot for the various catalyst reusing cycles carried out according to the procedure described in the text for the SM reaction of 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene with phenyl boronic acid in EtOH: H₂O 96:4 v/v at 80 °C. Solid lines stand for the linear last-squares fitting of experimental values to Eq.(1). Cycle order: 1 (●); 2 (○); 3 (■); 4 (□); 5 (s); 6 (△); 7 (◆).

at the beginning of the reaction, but it moved away from linearity as the process progressed. Assuming that the slope was proportional to the catalytic activity, the graph is showing the catalyst deactivation in real time. Accordingly, the amount of Pd initially dissolved speed up the conversion. This Pd was always involved in the SM cycle, thereby its activity was not appreciably changing with time. In this situation, the rate constant remained a constant and $F_{11}(x)$ behaved linearly, as observed. Nevertheless, the substrate concentration decreased as reaction progressed making a larger number of Pd centers to remain unoccupied. As a result, the metal aggregates, decreasing the number of catalytic centers in solution. This phenomenon slowed down the reaction, and it caused the loss of linearity.

For the remainder cycles, $F_{11}(x)$ behaved linearly all-time but the slope reduced in a large extent as the number of cycles raised. This observation was rationalized considering that the recovered catalyst produced initially lower quantities of soluble Pd (consumed in the previous cycle), resulting in a [substrate]/[solubilized Pd] ratio that gradually increased among cycles. In this situation, there were fewer possibilities for the aggregate formation, which kept the catalytic activity constant, but reducing the substrate conversion rate. This phenomenon was more pronounced in subsequent cy-

cles as the amount of potential soluble Pd adsorbed on silica was increasingly scarce. As more cycles were performed, the more nanoclusters disappeared by the process of aggregation/deposition reducing to almost 1/80 the catalyst activity as assess Table 3.

4.3. Classical Tests to Check the Homogeneous vs. Heterogeneous Nature of Catalysis

The previous results suggest that dissolved Pd is probably responsible for most of the substrate conversion. In order to verify this point, a number of experiments were carried out, specifically hot filtering, centrifugation, poisoning experiments, and the three phases test.

Hot Filtrate and Centrifugation Experiments. Hot filtrate and centrifugation experiments are classic tests to check the existence of leaching catalyst species. The methods differ in the way the catalyst is separated from the reaction mixture, either by centrifugation or filtration. In this study, both filtrates were not active, as it becomes evident that reaction stopped at 62% of conversion after catalyst removal (Figure S5). With these results, filtration/centrifugation tests may be misleading.³⁹ In the case of the hot filtration test, Pd species in solution can be deposited on the support when the liquid phase is forced to flow through the silica as temperature drops during filtering.⁴⁴ This phenomenon can also occur for separation by centrifugation.

Poisoning Catalyst Experiments. Capture of Pd by means of reactive groups, for example -NH₂ or -SH, attached on silica or another macromolecular support has been extensively used for detecting active Pd in solution.³⁹ If the catalyst leaches Pd species, their removal by reacting on the anchored groups will lead to a decrease in the reaction rate. The rate drop will be so much more drastic as more important the homogeneous process is. In this experiment, 3-mercaptopropyl-silicagel (MPSG), and Quadrapure TU were used as Pd sequestering compounds. MPSG was added at zero time, and Quadrapure TU, 4 minutes after the reaction began. Figure S5 shows that a sharp slowdown was produced, especially when the more active MPSG was added, stopping almost completely the progress of the reaction. This result indicated the catalytic process was mainly driven by dissolved Pd molecular species, concurring completely with the results of kinetic experiments. However, this result could be misleading because the poison is able remove any type of catalytic species, i.e. it is not selective.²⁴ On the other hand, this result was not in conflict with the hot filtration test, in which the lack of activity should be interpreted as an elimination of soluble Pd by interaction with the silica

869 during filtering/cooling process, and not as an absence
870 of Pd leaching.

871 *Three Phases Test.* The three phases test is consid-
872 ered a effective tool to check the presence of homoge-
873 neous catalytic activity of supported Pd catalysts.^{41,42,53}
874 It is based on the study of the products of a SM reaction
875 carried out using together a 4-substitutedphenyl halide
876 in solution and other immobilized on a support such
877 as silica. For pure heterogeneous processes, the cata-
878 lyst is not able to interact with the supported substrate,
879 but in case of the catalysis has a homogeneous compo-
880 nent both 4-substitutedphenyl halides undergo conver-
881 sion. Each case can be tested as the reaction products
882 differ (Scheme S2).

883 Two experiments were carried out, differing
884 in the amount of aminofunctionalized silicagel
885 (BrPhCONH-SiO₂) added (450 or 100 mg), and in
886 the ratio 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene:phenylboronic acid
887 used (1:1,5 or 1:7,5). A sample of the first reaction
888 mixture was analyzed by HPLC after 90 minutes, a time
889 proper to exhaust completely the substrate. Amazingly,
890 HPLC analysis revealed that reaction had not made any
891 progress, as all 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene was recovered.
892 Obviously, the substrate should have been consumed
893 regardless of whether the reaction was homogeneous
894 or heterogeneous. This observation suggested that the
895 catalytic process was stopped by removal of dissolved
896 Pd, probably by absorption in the huge amount of
897 aminofunctionalized silicagel employed. To check this
898 point, the experiment was repeated, but replacing the
899 aminofunctionalized silica by unfunctionalized silica
900 (UVM-7, 500 mg), observing that reaction stopped as in
901 the previous case. This behavior was observed by Ellis
902 et col.²⁷ This observation can be interpreted in different
903 ways. The obvious for us is the smallest fraction of
904 solubilized Pd enters within the pore network of UVM-
905 7 silica, which results in mass-transport limitations
906 leading to much slower reaction kinetics. This is an
907 equilibrium process which removes solubilized Pd.
908 However, Ellis et col. consider that reaction delaying
909 provides further indirect evidence for surface-driven
910 catalysis.²⁷

911 Consequently, a new test was conducted by adding
912 5 times more phenylboronic acid to speed up the reac-
913 tion, and decreasing the amount aminofunctionalized
914 silicagel to 100 mg, to reduce the probability of Pd sol-
915 ule species to be trapped. Under these conditions, the
916 reaction experienced approximately 33% conversion in
917 24 hours. The sample was treated as described in the ex-
918 perimental section, and its ¹H NMR spectrum recorded,
919 see Figure S6. ¹H NMR spectrum was fully consist-
920 ent with the presence of 4-bromobenzoic acid (signals

Figure 4: Differential selectivity results. Reaction catalyzed by [PdCl₂(CH₃CN)₂](x₁/x₂): (s) 4-bromoanisole/4-bromoacetophenone, (●) 4-bromoanisole/4-bromotoluene, (■) 4-iodoanisole/4-iodotoluene; Reaction catalyzed by Pd NPs UVM-7 (x₁/x₂): (Δ) 4-bromoanisole/4-bromoacetophenone, (○) 4-bromoanisole/4-bromotoluene, (□) 4-iodoanisole/4-iodotoluene. T=80°C in EtOH:H₂O 96:4 v/v, base K₂CO₃.

921 at 7,98 and 7,64 ppm, integration ratio 2:2) and [1,1'-
922 biphenyl]-4-carboxylic acid (signals at 8,19, 7,72, and
923 7,51 ppm, inte-gration ratio 2:2:3) in an approximate
924 ratio 85:15. The presence of both products confirmed
925 that solubilized Pd species are involved in the catalytic
926 process (included colloidal Pd).²⁴

927 4.4. Schmidt's Analysis of Differential Selectivity

928 Crabtree² indicated that the more reliable experi-
929 ments to distinguish between soluble or supported cat-
930 alytic activity are those not involving additives, for ex-
931 ample the kinetic methods. Furthermore, Schmidt et
932 col. propose the study of the differential selectivity ex-
933 periments involving structurally similar substrates hav-
934 ing different substitutes that are remote from the reac-
935 tion center.³⁰ This method has been successfully ap-
936 plied to SM and HM reactions.

937 Accordingly, a series of SADS measurements were
938 performed with the aim of compare the activity of
939 [PdCl₂(CNCH₃)₂] (soluble catalyst) to that of PdNPs-
940 UVM-7. In SADS, the concentrations of the biphenylic
941 compounds, x₁ = [Ph-PhR₁] and x₂ = [Ph-PhR₂], re-
942 sulting from kinetics in which two aryl halides compete
943 for the same catalyst are measured. The theory states
944 that the trajectories x₂ = f(x₁) in the phase plane (x₁, x₂)
945 of both reactive systems must overlap when the catalytic
946 species are analogous for both catalysts. If this were not
947 the case, divergent trajectories should be observed.

948 Figure 4 shows the trajectories on the plane phase 999
949 for the 4-bromoanisole/4-bromo-acetophenone, 4- 1000
950 bromo-anisole/4-bromotoluene, and 4-iodo-anisole/4- 1001
951 iodotoluene systems. Attempts to measure the 1002
952 4-iodo-anisole/4-iodo-acetophenone system resulted 1003
953 in non significant results due to the high rate at 1004
954 which the reaction proceeded. The graph shows the 1005
955 concentration of the more reactive system (x_2) in 1006
956 front of the slower one (x_1) for each couple. Figure 1007
957 4 states that each pair shares a common trajectory, 1008
958 which fit to a straight line within the experimental 1009
959 error. Furthermore, the slope of the lines is related 1010
960 with the relative reactivity of each pair. Thereby, the 1011
961 plot of [4-bromo-acetophenone] vs. [4-bromo-anisole] 1012
962 presents a slope of 10.0 which concurs with the higher 1013
963 reactivity of 4-bromo-acetophenone with regard to 1014
964 4-bromo-anisole, whereas the corresponding graphs 1015
965 of the 4-bromo-anisole/4-bromotoluene and 4-iodo- 1016
966 anisole/4-iodotoluene pairs have slopes of 0.98 and 0.92 1017
967 respectively. For these systems, the reactivity of the 1018
968 OCH₃ and CH₃ substituted aryl halide is quite similar. 1019
969 Differential selectivity experiments suggest that the 1020
970 catalytic species are similar for [PdCl₂(CNCH₃)₂] and 1021
971 PdNPs-UVM-7. Therefore, it is correct to conclude that 1022
972 the dissolved species of Pd drive mainly the catalytic 1023
973 action of Pd-NPs-UVM-7. 1024

974 4.5. STEM-HAADF Characterization of the Catalyst 1026 975 Along the Reusing Cycles 1027

976 The model deduced from the kinetic study is sup- 1028
977 ported by the electron microscopy images recorded after 1029
978 each reusing cycles previously described. The STEM- 1030
979 HAADF images and their respective histograms show- 1031
980 ing the Pd NPs particle size distributions are gathered 1032
981 in 6. For the first time, we present a stepped sequence 1033
982 of images that span the catalyst evolution up to 7th re- 1034
983 action cycle. Previous similar analysis described in the 1035
984 bibliography focused their attention on the comparison 1036
985 between the initial catalyst and the end after several cy- 1037
986 cles, without showing their evolution progressively. 1038

987 The catalyst after a single reaction cycle was very 1039
988 similar to the starting solid NPs Pd-UVM-7. A similar 1040
989 behavior was observed by Köhler et col.⁴⁵ It retained an 1041
990 excellent dispersion of Pd NPs, which have only slightly 1042
991 increased their average size (3.5 nm) with respect to the 1043
992 starting solid (2.7 nm). No aggregates of Pd NPs were 1044
993 observed, which manifested into a narrow particle size 1045
994 distribution. Köhler et col. analyzed the Pd distribution 1046
995 only after the first cycle. However, in our case, a drastic 1047
996 change in size and structure of Pd clusters was observed 1048
997 in subsequent cycles. As the reaction cycles increased 1049
998 (between 3 and 5 cycles), a progressive increase of the 1050

maximum in the sizes distribution was observed: 6 and 8.5 nm for the catalyst after 3 and 5 cycles respectively. However, the most remarkable fact was the progressive increase of aggregates of Pd NPs that grow both in number and size. Finally, after the last cycle, although a certain proportion of isolated particles or small aggregates smaller than 10 nm were still observed, most of the palladium was forming large aggregates up to 250 nm in size. This localized palladium enrichment also supposed the loss of it in other regions of the catalyst, in which Pd NPs were practically not detected. This evolution was correlated with a very important decrease of activity, as the particles, when growing and adding, form large clusters offering a smaller surface to the organic substrates. Furthermore, it can be assumed that migrating of Pd from the silica surface to the solution will be even more difficult from the larger aggregates. Consequently, an evolution from a reaction mechanism, very similar to those labeled as homogeneous (mainly driven by dissolved Pd), to a heterogeneous one (mainly driven by the supported Pd) occurs. This qualitative tendency fits very well with the quantitative model based on the kinetic study. The observed growth of the Pd aggregates on the solid catalyst illustrates the hypothesized dissolution/redeposition process of Pd by the end of the reaction also observed in the HM reaction, which is considered for some authors as an homogeneous process.⁵²

The high angle XRD patterns unambiguously shows the absence of diffraction peaks even for the catalyst in which larger Pd NPs aggregates exist (Figure S1). This fact is in good accordance with HRTEM images shown in Figure 5. Regardless the number of catalytic cycles, all images show the existence of crystalline nanoparticles with interplanar distances typical of metallic Pd(0). However, the increase in size of the aggregates does not imply an increase in the size of the individual nanoparticles. Thus, the crystallite size always remains below ca. 10 nm, a limit value for detecting palladium by X-ray diffraction techniques. In addition, the relatively low proportion of Pd in the catalyst is also not favorable for its detection.

The successive catalytic cycles have a clear influence on the silica network, that manifests in the low-angle XRD patterns and in the N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms (Figure S2). After the first catalytic cycle, the diffractogram of the material still shows a shoulder that could be assigned to the intense reflection (100) assuming a hexagonal cell. For the catalyst after additional cycles, this signal is lost. This evolution indicates an increase of the disorder, or even a partial or total mesostructure collapse. On the other hand, the de-

Figure 5: STEM-HAADF and Pd particle size distributions. PdNPs-UVM-7 after 1 (a,b,c), 3 (d,e,f), 5 (g,h,i) and 7 (j,k,l) catalytic cycles.

crease of the BET area as well as the marked reduction of the mesopore volume ($P/P_0 < 0.5$) with the number of cycles, is more suggestive of an important collapse than of a simple disorganization. The factor responsible for this degradation of silica seems to be the basic pH conditions derived from the use of K_2CO_3 . In any case, the larger pore system of textural type is not so affected by the basic conditions used. Although there is a progressive decrease in the BET area and the BJH macropore volume between the third and 7th cycles, it is much less marked. In any case, the large interparticle pore system still maintains, after 7 cycles, a sufficient size and volume for the diffusion of the organic substrate or the release (and subsequent incorporation) of Pd NPs. Therefore, the catalyst deactivation seems to be more related to the aggregation (and possible fixation) of large aggregates of Pd NPS on the silica surface.

5. Conclusions

The use of an organometallic Pd precursor allowed the synthesis of very small and dispersed Pd NPs on the surface of UVM-7 silica. The synthesized material has a high catalytic activity in the SM reaction, especially against 4-substituted phenyl iodides/bromides. Despite the lack of detailed kinetic data collected in the literature, comparison of the activity respect to other materials indicates that the synthesized catalyst is, at least initially, as active as the unsupported Pd nanoclusters prepared in the presence of stabilizing agents. The kinetic study strongly suggests that the molecular Pd species that migrate from the surface of the silica towards the solution are responsible for most of the catalytic activity. These Pd species suffer a growing process in solution when they are not involved in the catalytic process, and subsequently they are deposited on the silica surface as extensive aggregates having poor catalytic activity.⁵² Structural studies carried out on the catalyst during the deactivation process also indicate that the Pd domains grow up progressively on the silica surface by capturing Pd species from solution rather than by crystalline growth, which is fully consistent with the conclusions derived from the kinetic model.

These results indicate that the design of synthesis strategies of active Pd catalysts for C-C coupling reactions should be targeted to yield small and dispersed Pd NPs (in stabilizing media) rather than low-leaching anchored Pd species. In our case, silica-supported Pd NPs have shown to be as active as those in solution. The comparative advantage of supported materials is the

Figure 6: Representative HRTEM images of (a) the isolated Pd NPs on the PdNPs-UVM-7 catalyst after 3 cycles and NPs aggregates after (b) 5, and (c) 7 cycles.

elimination of the soluble Pd by filtration at low temperature through the own silica support.

Finally, it is worth stressing that our conclusions support the recently developed concept of “cocktail” of catalysts and the dynamic nature of the catalytic systems.¹⁷

Supporting Information

XRD results (Figure S1). N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms of PdNPs-UVM-7 (Figure S2). UVM-7 silica synthesis. Dependence of reaction rate on catalyst (Figure S3, Table S1) and phenylboronic concentrations (Figure S4, Table S2). Theoretical rate law (Scheme S1). Poisoning and hot filtration results (Figure S5). Three phases test reactions (Scheme S2). Three phases test ¹H RMN results (Figure S6).

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References

[1] I. P. Beletskaya, A. V. Cheprakov, The Heck reaction as a sharpening stone of palladium catalysis, *Chem. Rev.* (2000) 3009–3066.

[2] R. Crabtree, Resolving heterogeneity problems and impurity artifacts in operationally homogeneous transition metal catalysts, *Chem. Rev.* 112 (2012) 1536–1554.

[3] M. T. Reetz, J. G. de Vries, Ligand-free Heck reactions using low Pd-loading, *Chem. Commun.* (2004) 1559–1563.

[4] de Vries J. G., A unifying mechanism for all high-temperature Heck reactions. the role of palladium colloids and anionic species, *Dalton Trans.* (2006) 421–429.

[5] C. Deraedt, D. Astruc, "Homeopathic" palladium nanoparticle catalysis of cross carbon-carbon coupling reactions, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 47 (2014) 494–503.

[6] A. Corma, H. Garcia, Crossing the borders between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis: Developing recoverable and reusable catalytic systems, *Top. Catal.* 48 (2008) 8–31.

[7] D. Astruc, F. Lu, J. Ruiz-Aranzaes, Nanoparticles as recyclable catalysts: The frontier between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 44 (2005) 7852–7872.

[8] D. Astruc, Palladium nanoparticles as efficient green homogeneous and heterogeneous carbon-carbon coupling precatalysts: a unifying view, *Inorg. Chem.* 46 (2007) 1884–1894.

[9] A. Fihri, M. Bouhrara, B. Nekoueishahraki, J. Basset, V. Polshettiwar, Nanocatalysts for Suzuki cross-coupling reactions, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 40 (2011) 5181–5203.

[10] A. Balanta, C. Godard, C. Claver, Pd nanoparticles for C-C coupling reactions, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 40 (2011) 4973–4985.

[11] L. Yin, J. Liebscher, Carbon-carbon coupling reactions catalyzed by heterogeneous palladium catalysts, *Chem. Rev.* 107 (2007) 133–173.

[12] G. Budroni, A. Corma, H. Garca, A. Primo, Pd nanoparticles embedded in sponge-like porous silica as a Suzuki-Miyaura catalyst: Similarities and differences with homogeneous catalysts, *J. Catal.* 251 (2007) 345–353.

[13] V. Polshettiwar, C. Len, A. Fihri, Silica-supported palladium: Sustainable catalysts for cross-coupling reactions, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 253 (2009) 2599–2626.

[14] M. Lamblin, L. NassarHardy, J. Hierso, E. Fouquet, F. Felpin, Recyclable heterogeneous palladium catalysts in pure water: Sustainable developments in Suzuki, Heck, Sonogashira and Tsuji-Trost reactions, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 352 (2010) 33–79.

[15] M. Pérez-Lorenzo, Palladium nanoparticles as efficient catalysts for Suzuki cross-coupling reactions, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 3 (2012) 167–174.

[16] P. Taladriz-Blanco, P. Hervés, J. Pérez-Juste, Supported Pd nanoparticles for carbon-carbon coupling reactions, *Top. Catal.* 56 (2013) 1154–1170.

[17] D. B. Eremin, V. P. Ananikov, Understanding active species in catalytic transformations: From molecular catalysis to nanoparticles, leaching, cocktails of catalysts and dynamic systems, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 346 (2017) 2–19.

[18] A. Biffis, P. Centomo, A. Del Zotto, M. Zecca, Pd metal catalysts for cross-couplings and related reactions in the 21st century: A critical review, *Chem. Rev.* 118 (2018) 2249–2295.

[19] V. M. Wall, A. Eisenstadt, D. J. Ager, S. A. Laneman, The Heck reaction and cinnamic acid synthesis by heterogeneous catalysis, *Platinum Met. Rev.* 43 (1999) 130–145.

[20] A. Biffis, M. Zecca, M. Basato, Platinum metal catalysis in Heck C-C coupling reactions, *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* 173 (2001) 249–274.

[21] A. Kurokhtina, E. V. Larina, A. F. Schmidt, Measuring the kinetic isotope effect at natural isotopic abundances for discriminating between the homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic mechanisms in the Heck and Suzuki reactions, *Kinet. Catal.* 57 (2016) 3441.

[22] G. Martra, L. Bertinetti, C. Gerbaldi, R. Maggi, G. Sartori, S. Coluccia, Pd/SiO₂ as heterogeneous catalyst for the Heck reaction: Evidence for a sensitivity to the surface structure of supported particles, *Catalysis Letters* 132 (2009) 50–57.

[23] M. Islam, P. Mondal, A. S. Roy, K. Tuhina, Use of a recyclable poly(n-vinyl carbazole) palladium(II) complex catalyst: Heck cross-coupling reaction under phosphine-free and aerobic conditions, *Transition Metal Chemistry* 35 (2010) 491–499.

[24] A. F. Schmidt, A. A. Kurokhtina, Distinguishing between the homogeneous and heterogeneous mechanisms of catalysis in the Mizoroki-Heck and Suzuki-Miyaura reactions: Problems and prospects, *Kinet. Catal.* 53 (2012) 714–730.

[25] C. Rossy, J. Majimel, E. Fouquet, C. Delacôte, M. Boujtita, C. Labrugère, M. TréguerDelapierre, F. Felpin, Stabilisation of carbon-supported palladium nanoparticles through the formation of an alloy with gold: Application to the Sonogashira reaction, *Chem. Eur. J.* 19 (2013) 14024–14029.

[26] R. Narayanan, C. Tabor, M. A. El-Sayed, Can the observed changes in the size or shape of a colloidal nanocatalyst reveal the nanocatalysis mechanism type: Homogeneous or heterogeneous?, *Top. Catal.* 48 (2008) 60–74.

[27] J. Ellis P., S. Fairlamb I. J., J. Hackett S. F., K. Wilson, F. Lee A., Evidence for the surface-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura reaction over palladium nanoparticles: An operando XAS study, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 49 (2010) 1820–1824.

[28] N. T. S. Phan, M. V. D. Sluys, C. W. Jones, On the nature of the active species in palladium catalyzed Mizoroki-Heck and Suzuki-Miyaura couplings-homogeneous or heterogeneous catalysis, a critical review, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 348 (2006) 609–679.

[29] J. A. Widegren, R. G. Finke, A review of the problem of distinguishing true homogeneous catalysis from soluble or other metal-particle heterogeneous catalysis under reducing conditions, *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* 198 (2003) 317–341.

[30] A. F. Schmidt, A. A. Kurokhtina, E. V. Larina, Simple kinetic method for distinguishing between homogeneous and heterogeneous mechanisms of catalysis, illustrated by the example of "ligand-free" Suzuki and Heck reactions of aryl iodides and aryl bromides, *Kinet. Catal.* 53 (2012) 86–93.

[31] G. Collins, M. Schmidt, C. O'Dwyer, J. D. Holmes, G. P. McGlacken, The origin of shape sensitivity in palladium-

- 1226 catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura cross coupling reactions, *Angew.* 1291
 1227 *Chem. Int. Ed.* 53 (2014) 4142–4145. 1292
- 1228 [32] A. LeyvaPérez, J. Oliver-Meseguer, P. Rubio-Marqués, 1293
 1229 A. Corma, Waterstabilized three and fouratom palladium clusters 1294
 1230 as highly active catalytic species in ligandfree C-C cross- 1295
 1231 coupling reactions, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 52 (2013) 11554– 1296
 1232 11559. 1297
- 1233 [33] F. Fu, J. Xiang, H. Cheng, L. Cheng, H. Chong, S. Wang, P. Li, 1298
 1234 S. Wei, M. Shu, Y. Li, A robust and efficient Pd₃ cluster catalyst 1299
 1235 for the Suzuki reaction and its odd mechanism, *ACS Catal.* 7 1300
 1236 (2017) 1860–1867. 1301
- 1237 [34] C. W. Jones, On the stability and recyclability of supported 1302
 1238 metal–ligand complex catalysts: Myths, misconceptions and 1303
 1239 critical research needs, *Top. Catal.* 53 (2010) 942–952. 1304
- 1240 [35] A. A. Kurokhtina, E. V. Larina, A. F. Shmidt, Study of the dif- 1305
 1241 ferential selectivity of cross-coupling reactions for elucidating 1306
 1242 the nature of the true catalyst, *Kinet. Catal.* 56 (2015) 191–197. 1307
- 1243 [36] J. El Haskouri, J. M. Morales, D. Ortiz de Zrate, L. Fernandez, 1308
 1244 J. Latorre, C. Guillem, A. Beltrn, D. Beltrn, P. Amors, Nanopar- 1309
 1245 ticulated silicas with bimodal porosity: Chemical control of the 1310
 1246 pore sizes, *Inorg. Chem.* 47 (2008) 8267–8277. 1311
- 1247 [37] F. Estevan, A. García-Bernabé, P. Lahuerta, M. Sanaú, M. A. 1312
 1248 Ubeda, M. C. Ramírez de Arellano, Synthesis, reactivity, and X- 1313
 1249 ray crystallographic characterization of mono-, di-, and tetranu- 1314
 1250 clear palladium(II)-metalated species, *Inorg. Chem.* 39 (2000) 1315
 1251 5964–5969. 1316
- 1252 [38] A. M. Aarif, F. Estevan, A. García-Bernabé, P. Lahuerta, 1317
 1253 M. Sanaú, M. A. Ubeda, Synthesis and X-ray crystal- 1318
 1254 lographic characterization of (μ -(diphenylphosphino)phenyl- 1319
 1255 C²²)₂Palladium bromide. A novel tetranuclear metalated com-
 1256 pound, *Inorg. Chem.* 36 (1997) 6472–6475.
- 1257 [39] J. M. Richardson, C. W. Jones, Poly(4vinylpyridine) and 1317
 1258 Quadrapure TU as selective poisons for soluble catalytic species 1318
 1259 in palladiumcatalyzed coupling reactions - application to leach- 1319
 1260 ing from polymerentrapped palladium, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 348
 1261 (2006) 1207–1216.
- 1262 [40] C. M. Crudden, M. Sateesh, R. Lewis, Mercaptopropyl- 1317
 1263 modified mesoporous silica: a remarkable support for the prepara- 1318
 1264 tion of a reusable, heterogeneous palladium catalyst for cou- 1319
 1265 pling reactions, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (2005) 10045–10050.
- 1266 [41] M. L. Kantam, M. Roy, S. Roy, B. Sreedhar, S. S. Madhava- 1317
 1267 dra, B. Choudary, R. L. De, Polyaniline supported palla- 1318
 1268 dium catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling of bromo- and 1319
 1269 chloroarenes in water, *Tetrahedron* 63 (2007) 8002 – 8009.
- 1270 [42] H. Gruber-Woelfler, P. F. Radaschitz, P. W. Feenstra, W. Haas, 1317
 1271 J. G. Khinast, Synthesis, catalytic activity, and leaching stud- 1318
 1272 ies of a heterogeneous Pd-catalyst including an immobilized 1319
 1273 bis(oxazoline) ligand, *J. Catal.* 286 (2012) 30 – 40.
- 1274 [43] J. Bezanson, S. Karpinski, V. B. Shah, A. Edelman, Julia: 1317
 1275 A fast dynamic language for technical computing, *CoRR* 1318
 1276 abs/1209.5145 (2012).
- 1277 [44] S. MacQuarrie, J. H. Horton, J. Barnes, K. McEleney, H. Loock, 1317
 1278 C. M. Crudden, Visual observation of redistribution and dissolu- 1318
 1279 tion of palladium during the Suzuki-Miyaura reaction, *Angew.* 1319
 1280 *Chem. Int. Ed.* 47 (2008) 3279–3282.
- 1281 [45] S. Soomro, F. L. Ansari, K. Chatziapostolou, K. Köhler, Pal- 1317
 1282 ladium leaching dependent on reaction parameters in Suzuki- 1318
 1283 Miyaura coupling reactions catalyzed by palladium supported 1319
 1284 on alumina under mild reaction conditions, *J. Catal.* 273 (2010) 138 – 146.
- 1285 [46] K. Köhler, R. G. Heidenreich, S. Soomro, S. S. Pröckl, Sup- 1317
 1286 ported palladium catalysts for Suzuki reactions: Structure- 1318
 1287 property relationships, optimized reaction protocol and control 1319
 1288 of palladium leaching, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 350 (2008) 2930– 1319
 1289 2936.
- [47] K. Köhler, W. Kleist, S. Pröckl, Genesis of coordinatively un- 1317
 saturated palladium complexes dissolved from solid precursors 1318
 during Heck coupling reactions and their role as catalytically 1319
 active species, *Inorg. Chem.* 46 (2007) 1876–1883.
- [48] S. S. Pröckl, W. Kleist, G. M. A., K. Köhler, In situ gener- 1317
 ation of highly active dissolved palladium species from solid 1318
 catalysts-a concept for the activation of aryl chlorides in the 1319
 Heck reaction, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 43
 (2004) 1881–1882.
- [49] Y. Nishihara (Ed.), *Applied Cross-Coupling Reactions*, vol- 1317
 ume 80 of *Lecture Notes in Chemistry*, Springer-Verlag Berlin 1318
 Heidelberg, 2013.
- [50] D. A. Conlon, B. Pipik, S. Ferdinand, C. R. LeBlond, J. R. 1317
 Sowa, B. Izzo, P. Collins, G. Ho, J. M. Williams, Y. Shi, Y. Sun, 1318
 Suzuki-Miyaura crosscoupling with quasiheterogeneous palla- 1319
 dium, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 345 (2003) 931–935.
- [51] T. E. Barder, S. D. Walker, J. R. Martinelli, S. L. Buchwald, Cat- 1317
 alysts for Suzuki-Miyaura coupling processes: scope and studies 1318
 of the effect of ligand structure, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (2005) 1319
 4685–4696.
- [52] S. Reimann, J. Stötzel, R. Frahm, W. Kleist, J. D. Grunwaldt, 1317
 A. Baiker, Identification of the active species generated from 1318
 supported pd catalysts in heck reactions: An in situ quick scan- 1319
 ning EXAFS investigation., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (2011) 3921–3030.
- [53] J. D. Webb, S. MacQuarrie, K. McEleney, C. M. Crudden, 1317
 Mesoporous silica-supported Pd catalysts: An investigation into 1318
 structure, activity, leaching and heterogeneity, *J. Catal.* 252 1319
 (2007) 97 – 109.